

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology

Title of the course: **Pharmacology I** Course number:

Level: 3rd Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours/week : **Theory 3**

Reference text: **Lipincott Pharmacology** . latest edition.

Objectives: To introduce the pharmacy students to the basis of general pharmacology. The student will learn about various body systems and drugs used to affect them in health and disease. Moreover the course will cover the drugs used to treat microbial infections.

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	General introduction to Pharmacology, Pharmacokinetics	4
2	Pharmacodynamics, Drug Receptor interaction.	4
3	Principles of antimicrobial therapy.	2
4	β - lactam and other cell wall synthesis inhibitor antibiotics	4
5	Protein synthesis inhibitors	4
6	Quinolones, Folate antagonists, and urinary tract antiseptics.	3
7	Antimycobacterium drugs	2
8	Antifungal drugs.	2
9	Antiprotozoal drugs.	2
10	Anthelmintic drugs.	1
11	Antiviral drugs.	2
12	Cancer Chemotherapy	7
13	Immunosuppressant	3
14	Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and other anti-inflammatory agents	3
15	Vitamines	2

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Laboratory Sciences

Title of the course: **Biochemistry I** Course number:

Level: 3rd Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours/week: **Theory 3 Laboratory 1**

Reference text: **Harper's Illustrated Biochemistry**. latest edition.

Objectives: To integrate key concepts describing the traditional core topics of Biochemistry: structure and metabolism. At the end of the semester the students should be able to understand the chemical structure, and function of all biomolecules present in the living organisms

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Introduction to the macromolecules biochemistry: Definitions and terms; proteins, enzymes, DNA; Clinical value.	2
2	Amino acids: Structures of A.A (table of standard A.A abbreviation and side chain); Classification, properties, isomerism.	3
3	Amino acids: Chemical reactions, Zwitter ions, titration curve calculating isoelectric point values. Examples and questions. Non standards A.A: Structures, existence and clinical value.	3
4	Peptides: Peptide bond, resonance forms, isomers, physical properties and chemical reactions. Essential poly peptides in human body, structures, roles and clinical values.	3
5	Proteins: Structure and conformations of proteins, Primary structure, Secondary structure (4 helix, 5 sheet), tertiary structure, quaternary structure. Classification, synthesis, cellular functions (Enzymes, cell signaling, and ligand transport, structural proteins), protein in nutrition	3
6	Denaturation of proteins and protein sequencing: Determining A.A composition, N- terminal A.A analysis, C- terminal A.A analysis, Edman degradation, prediction protein sequence from DNA/ RNA sequences. Methods of protein study: Protein purification, cellular localization, proteomics and bioinformatics, structure predication and simulation.	3
7	Carbohydrates: Chemistry and classification, biomedical importance, classification of CHO, Stereochemistry of monosaccharides, metabolism of CHO; Physiologically important monosaccharides, glycosides, disaccharides, polysaccharides.	3
8	Lipids: Introduction, classification of lipids, fatty acids (F.A),	3

	nomenclature of F.A, saturated F.A, unsaturated F.A, physical and physiological properties of F.A, metabolism of lipids. Phospholipids, lipid peroxidation and antioxidants, separation and identification of lipids, amphipathic lipids.	
9	Enzymes: Structures and mechanism, nomenclature, classification, mechanisms of catalysis, thermodynamics, specificity, lock and key model, induced fit model, transition state stabilization, dynamics and function, allosteric modulation. Biological function, cofactors, coenzymes, involvement in disease	3
10	Kinetics: General principles, factors effecting enzyme rates (substrate conc., pH, temperature, etc), single-substrate reaction (Michaelis- Menten kinetics), kinetic constants. Examples of kinetic questions and solutions	2
11	Enzyme inhibition: Reversible inhibitors, competitive and non competitive inhibition, mixed-type inhibition, Irreversible inhibition. Inhibition kinetics and binding affinities (K_i), questions and solutions.	1
12	Control of activity and uses of inactivators; multi-substrate reactions, ternary-complex mechanisms, ping-pong mechanisms, non-Michaelis- Menten kinetics, pre-steady-state kinetics, chemical mechanisms	1
13	Nucleic Acid: Chemical structure, nucleic acid components, nucleic acid bases, nucleotides and deoxynucleotides (Properties, base pairing, sense and antisense, super-coiling, alternative structures, quadruple structures.	3
14	Biological functions of DNA: Genes and genomes, transcription and translation, replication.	2
15	Biochemistry of extracellular and intracellular communication: Plasma membrane structure and function; Biomedical importance, membrane proteins associated with lipid bilayer, membranes protein composition, dynamic structures of membranes, a symmetric structures of membranes.	3
16	Artificial membranes model, the fluid mosaic model, membrane selectivity, physiological functions of plasma membranes.	1
17	Biochemistry of the endocrine system: Classification of hormones, biomedical importance, the target cell concept and hormone receptors, biochemistry of hormone signal transduction.	3
18	Special topics: Nutrition, digestion, and absorption. Biomedical importance, digestion and absorption of carbohydrates, lipids, proteins, vitamins and minerals; energy balance. Biochemistry of hemostasis and clot formation.	3

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Laboratory Sciences

Title of the course ***practical Biochemistry I***

Level: 3rd Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours/week : **1**

Reference text: ***Lab Manual for Practical Biochemistry Adopted by the Department***

Objectives: To integrate key concepts describing the traditional core topics of Biochemistry: structure and metabolism. At the end of the semester the students should be able to understand the chemical structure, and function of all biomolecules present in the living organisms.

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Effects of acids on carbohydrates: Molish test; Bials test; Anthron test; Seliwanoffs test; Mucic acid test.	2
2	Classification of carbohydrates according to reducing properties: Benedicts test; Fehlings test; Barfoed test.	2
3	Classification of carbohydrates according to reducing properties: Iodine test; Ozasone test.	2
4	Determination of unknown carbohydrates sample.	2
5	Color reactions of proteins: Biuret test; Ninhydrin test.	2
6	Color reactions of proteins: Millons test; Hopkins–Cole test; unoxidized sulfur test.	2
7	Solubility of proteins (effects of acid, neutral salts, heavy metals, and alkaloidal reagents).	2
8	Determination of unknown sample of proteins.	2
9	Experiments on solubility of lipids.	2
10	Acrolin test for lipids; Soap; Studying properties of soap.	2
11	Determination of saponification number.	2
12	Properties of lipids: Iodine test for lipids.	2
13	Properties of enzymes: Effects of heat on enzymes.	2
14	Properties of enzymes: Effect of concentration of enzyme (salivary amylase) on reaction velocity.	2
15	Properties of enzymes: Effect of pH on enzymatic activity.	2

University of Baghdad
College of Pharmacy
Department of Clinical Laboratory Sciences

Title of the course: ***Pathophysiology*** Course number:

Level: 3rd Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours/week : **Theory 3 Laboratory 1**

Reference text:

Essentials in Pathophysiology by: Carol Mattson Porth . latest edition.

Objectives: Describe the basic concepts of pathophysiology at the cellular level related to injury, the self-defense mechanism, mutation, and cellular proliferation. Outline basic pathological factors that influence the disease process. Describe the impact and abnormal functions upon the organ (s) associated with the disease process of targeted body systems. Describe clinical manifestations associated with the diseases.

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Introduction.	2
2	Cell injury and tissue response; Degeneration; Necrosis; Atrophy; Hypertrophy; Metaplasia and Calcification; Inflammation and Repair.	6
3	Disorders of electrolytes and water and acid-base balances: Hyper and Hyponatremia; Hyper and Hypokalemia; Syndrome of inappropriate secretion of ADH; Diabetes insipidus; Metabolic acidosis and alkalosis; Respiratory acidosis and alkalosis	4
4	Disorders of cardiovascular system: Hyperemia; Congestion and edema; Thrombosis; embolism and infarction; Shock; Coronary heart disease and MI; Rheumatic heart disease; Heart failure; Acute pulmonary edema; Essential hypertension; Secondary hypertension; Malignant hypertension; Hypotension; Aneurysm versus varicose veins	6

5	Disorders of respiratory system: Pneumonias; Tuberculosis; Respiratory distress syndrome; Bronchial asthma; Emphysema and bronchiectasis; Cystic fibrosis; Pulmonary embolism; Pulmonary hypertension.	5
6	Disorders of the renal system: Nephrotic syndrome; Glomerulonephritis; Diabetic glomerulosclerosis; Hypertensive glomerular disease; Pyelonephritis; Drug related nephropathies; Acute renal failure; Chronic renal failure.	5
7	Disorders of GI and hepatobiliary systems: Peptic ulcer and Zollinger –Ellison syndrome; Irritable bowel syndrome; Crohn's disease; Diarrhea; Celiac disease; Viral hepatitis; Primary biliary cirrhosis; Liver failure; Cholelithiasis.	5
8	Disorders of thyroid function: Hypothyroidism. Hyperthyroidism. Graves's disease. Thyrotoxicosis.	3
9	Disorders of adrenal function: Cushing syndrome. Adrenal cortical insufficiency (primary and secondary). Congenital adrenal hyperplasia. Pheochromocytoma	3
10	Diabetes mellitus and metabolic syndrome; Dyslipoproteinemia.	6

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Laboratory Sciences

Title of the course: ***Pathophysiology***

Level: 3rd Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours/week : **1**

Reference text: ***Lab Manual for Practical Pathophysiology Adopted by the Department.***

Objectives: Describe the basic concepts of pathophysiology at the cellular level related to injury, the self-defense mechanism, mutation, and cellular proliferation. Outline basic pathological factors that influence the disease process. Describe the impact and abnormal functions upon the organ (s) associated with the disease process of targeted body systems. Describe clinical manifestations associated with the diseased organ(s).

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	General introduction and slide preparation	2
2	Cell injury and degenerations.	2
3	Growth disturbances	2

4	Inflammation.	2
5	Thrombosis.	2
6	Neoplasia.	2
7	Disorders of respiratory system	2
8	Disorders of the cardiovascular system	2
9	Disorders of renal system	2
10	Liver disorders	2
11	Disorders of the gastrointestinal tract.	2
12	Disorders of the central nervous system	2
13	Disorders of the reproductive system.	2
14	Disorders of skeletomuscular system	2
15	Disorders of endocrine system.	2

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Pharmaceutics

Title of the course: ***Pharmaceutical Technology I*** Course number:

Level: 3rd Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours/week : **Theory 3 Laboratory 1**

Reference text: ***Pharmaceutical Dosage forms and Drug Delivery Systems By Haward A. Ansel; latest edition.*** and ***Sprowel's American Pharmacy.***

Objectives: To teach theoretical bases for the technology of preparing different dosage forms with respect to their raw materials, compositions, methods of preparation, stability, storage and uses.

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Dispersed systems: their classification; comparisons between different systems.	2
2	Solutions and types of solutions.	2
3	Solubility: Factors affecting solubility; expression of dissolution; dissolution rate versus solubility; preparation of solutions containing non-volatile materials.	4
4	Official solutions; classification of official solutions; preparation and uses.	4

5	Aqueous solutions containing aromatic principles; aromatic waters; methods of preparations; stability.	4
6	Syrups: sugar based syrups; artificial and sorbitol based syrups; stability of syrups.	4
7	Definition and methods of clarification; filter aids in clarification.	3
8	Preparation of solutions using mixed solvent systems; spirits, and elixirs.	3
9	Extraction; maceration and percolation.	3
10	Tinctures; fluid extracts; extracts of resins and oleoresins.	4
11	Colloidal dispersions; lyophilic; lyophobic.	6
12	Coarse dispersion; suspensions.	6

University of Baghdad

**College of Pharmacy Department
of Pharmaceutics**

Title of the course ***Pharmaceutical Technology I***

Level: 3rd Class, 1st Semester

Credit hours/week: **1**

Reference text: ***Lab manual for Practical Pharmaceutical Technology Adopted by the Department.***

Objectives: To teach theoretical bases for the technology of preparing different dosage forms with respect to their raw materials, compositions, methods of preparation, stability, storage

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Solutions (into body cavity, oral and external use).	4
2	Syrups: Preparation techniques and quality evaluation.	6

3	Elixirs: Preparation techniques and quality evaluation	4
4	Spirits: Preparation techniques and quality evaluation	6
5	Suspensions: Preparation techniques and quality evaluation.	4
6	Dispersion of oils in inhalations.	6

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical laboratory sciences

Title of the course: **Public health**

Level: **4th Class, 1st Semester**

Credit hours: **theory 2 hours.**

Reference:

1- Adetokunbo O. Lucas, Herbert M. Gillies. short textbook of public health medicine for the tropics. Latest edition.

2-Roger Detels, Martin Gulliford, Quarraisha Abdool Karim, et al. Oxford Textbook of Global Public Health. Latest edition.

3-Theodore H. Tulchinsky, Elena A. Varavikova, The New Public Health Latest edition.

4-Aliso Blenkinsopp, Rhona Panton, Claire Anderson. health promotion for pharmacist. Latest edition.

Objective:

This course enables the students to understand the principles of public health and the art of preventing disease, promoting health and prolonging life.

No	Lecture title	hours
1	Introduction: The scope and concerns of public health.	1
2	Health care system in Iraq	1
3	Measuring, Monitoring, and Evaluating the Health of a Population	2
4	Population screening and public health	1
5	Prevention and control of non-communicable diseases	2
6	Principles of infectious disease control	1
7	National immunization plan of Iraq.	1
8	Communicable diseases (infections through the gastro-intestinal tract, Infections through skin and mucous membranes, Infections through the respiratory tract)	4

9	Prevention and control of public health hazards (Tobacco, alcohol, Public health aspects of illicit psychoactive drug use)	4
10	Major health problems (Obesity, Physical activity and health, Public mental health and suicide, Dental public health, Sexually transmitted infections, Chronic hepatitis and other liver disease, Tuberculosis ...)	5
11	Nutritional disorders	2
12	Family health	2
13	Environmental health	1
14	Occupational health	1
15	Travel health	1
16	Health insurance	1